

CONSTRUCTION AND EVALUATION OF A BATTERY-ASSISTED GENERATOR SYSTEM FOR OFF-GRID APPLICATION

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Abstract: *Today, Nigeria faces a destabilizing dependency on irreplaceable fossil fuels, which are also rapidly dwindling. As shortages of oil and natural gas occur with more frequency, the “New Energy Crisis” is now heralded in the news media. However, an alternate source of energy that can replace fossil fuels has not been reliably demonstrated. A real need exists for a portable source of power that can compete with fossil fuels and their energy density. A further need exists on land, in the air, and in space, for an alternative source of power which, by definition, does not require refueling. The future freedom, and quite possibly the future survival, of mankind depend on the utilization of such a source of energy, if it exists. Electricity supply has been erratic for a long while in Nigeria, and over time, there is a need for new energy sources, which has led to some alternatives. Therefore, in order to find other ways of producing energy, some alternatives have been considered. One of these alternatives is the generation of electricity from a fuel-less electromechanically coupled engine in an isolated power generation system with low maintenance cost. In response to this, a battery-assisted generator was designed and developed using local materials. The driving mechanism of the generator is a direct current motor, powered by a 12-volt 62Ah battery, which spins the 12 V alternator to produce electricity, while recharging the battery by means of solar energy. The battery-assisted generator has an output of 1 kVA, and it is pollution-free and eco-friendly.*

Keywords: *Alternative energy, Battery-Assisted Generator, D.C Motor, Controller, fuel-less engine.*

Introduction

The global consumption of energy is growing, and there is a need for other forms of renewable energy sources, which are free from harmful emissions of carbon gases, to be looked into. Among the following energy resources that could be free from such harmful emissions are wind, wave, tidal, photovoltaic, and osmotic power, but a fuel-less engine is still the most dependable, low-maintenance cost energy renewable solution (Benhammon, et al., 2023). As of today in Nigeria, the use of conventional energy such as fossil fuel is still a major source of energy in powering residential homes and small commercial businesses, and this source of energy emits harmful carbon gases which causes pollution such as noise

and air pollution which in turn affect our surrounding environment. Despite the adverse effect on environment, the pressure on the environment by human activities coupled with carbon gases emission calls for thorough research on alternatives sources of energy (Muktar et al., 2025) which can increase electricity generation and bring about electricity revolution in Nigeria. Conventional electricity generators make use of fossil fuel (such as petrol, diesel, steam, charcoal, kerosene etc), in which an internal combustion process is involved in the engine using the chemical energy from the fuel to drive the alternator thereby generating electricity based on the principle of electromagnetic induction (Chalal and Rachid, 2025).

Today, Nigeria faces a destabilizing dependency on irreplaceable fossil fuels which are also rapidly dwindling giving rise to shortage of oil and natural gas which occurs frequently leading to energy crisis (Ayinla and Yusuf, 2018). Although, an alternative source of energy that can replace fossil fuel has not been reliable demonstrated however, there exist a real need for portable source of power that can compete with fossil fuels and its energy density (Hanafi et al., 2024) either on land, in air, in space, or from other fuel-less source of power which by definition, does not require re-fueling (Robert et al., 2020). The future freedom and survival of mankind which will depend on the utilization of such a source of energy, is quite possible if such energy is harnessed (Benhammon, et al., 2023). The future freedom for such survival has led to the design and construction of a battery-assisted generator using a fuel-less engine.

The fuel-less engine of the battery-assisted generator, which is capable of producing electricity regularly without fuel (petrol, diesel, oil, grease, gas, wind energy), is noiseless, pollution free, and self-dependent thereby having a positive impact on the environment (Ayinla and Yusuf, 2018) and can be constructed to the capacity of the load it is intended to carry. The driving mechanism is the D.C. Motor, which is driven by a battery (12V or more). The battery drives the D.C. Motor which in turn spins the alternator to produce electricity and at the same time, with the help of solar energy which recharges the battery externally. It requires a suitable controller to regulate the voltage due to the variation of the consumer loads.

Materials and Methods

The construction and evaluation of the battery-assisted generator for off-grid application involves the integration of various aspects such as component selection, system design, construction of the prototype, testing procedure and data analysis.

System Design

The battery-assisted power generating set consists of the major units, which includes the following:

(i) The Power Supply Unit

This unit serves as storage device for the direct current which is to be induced. A 12-volt battery was used as source of power supply unit to the DC motor in order to induce electromotive force (emf). Lead acid battery is highly recommended for DC generating system.

(ii) Conversion Unit

This unit is that which differentiates the DC generator from the general generating set that uses fuel as its source of energy. The unit is be responsible for all voltage current and power conversion that takes place in the generating system (Ajav and Adewumi, 2014). It also has a regulating conversion board which converts the 12 V supply to 48 V, thereby, regulating the power.

(iii) Control Unit

This unit converts direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC), and also performs the removal of ripples and rectification of alternating current signals (Gamazo-Real, et al., 2024). The size of the alternator been used will determine the capacity of the generating set.

(iv) Output Unit

The use of the control circuit that will make it possible to provide output voltage within the range of 100v to 240v which is the standard voltage required for all appliances. The red wire on the alternator was used to supply the household and offices as the mains.

(v) Charging Unit

A Charging unit refers to a charging process where the AC (Alternating Current) power in the electrical grid gets transformed into Direct Current (AC) which is what in electric vehicle (Ev) battery stories to supply the system back as a feedback supply (Chalal and Rachid, 2025).

The integration of the various units that make up the system design is shown in Figure 1

Figure 1: Block Diagram of battery-assisted generator (Roberts et al., 2020)

Construction/Design Procedures

The design and construction of the generating set were carried out through a sequence of systematic procedures. First, a crankshaft was fabricated with a borehole dimensioned to appropriately accommodate the DC motor shaft, including a threaded hole to allow the motor to be securely bolted to the crankshaft. The fabricated crankshaft was then coupled to the DC motor and the assembled unit was inserted into the crank casing of the alternator. Subsequently, the alternator armature was mounted within the casing, after which the stator housing was positioned over the armature. A long bolt was then inserted through the bearing end of the stator and firmly tightened to securely integrate the DC motor and the alternator assembly. Thereafter, the alternator cover was replaced and fastened to the crank casing. In order to ensure structural stability and mechanical support, a rigid frame was constructed to house the generator system. Finally, appropriate electrical connections were implemented: the diode connections were linked using green cables, the capacitor connections were made with yellow cables, the DC motor terminals were interfaced with the equivalent battery terminals, and the red cables were connected to serve as the mains output of the system.

Figure 2: Diagram of the battery-assisted generator

Working Principle

The battery-assisted generator operates on the principle of electromechanical energy conversion, in which electrical energy from a stored source is first converted into mechanical motion and subsequently reconverted into electrical energy through electromagnetic induction. In the developed system, a DC motor serves as the prime mover, while an alternator functions as the electrical energy conversion unit (Adewumi and Adelekan, 2020).

When the system is connected to a 12 V, 65 Ah deep cycle battery source, electrical current flows through the terminals of the DC motor, producing a magnetic field within the motor windings. According to the principle of Lorentz force, the interaction between the magnetic field and the current-carrying conductors produces a mechanical torque that causes the motor shaft to rotate (Chapman, 2012). The fabricated crankshaft, which is mechanically coupled to the motor shaft, transmits this rotational motion directly to the rotor (armature) of the alternator. The rigid coupling between the motor and alternator ensures efficient mechanical power transfer. As the alternator rotor begins to rotate within the stationary stator windings, a changing magnetic field is created around the stator conductors (Supriyatna, 2023). According to Faraday's Law of Electromagnetic Induction, any change in magnetic flux linking a conductor induces an electromotive force (EMF) in that conductor (Fitzgerald, et al., 2003). Consequently, alternating voltage is induced in the stator windings of the alternator. This generated voltage is then delivered through the output terminals of the generator AC output, which are connected via the designated output cables to the load and a 24 V, 60 A charger. The charger provides constant recharging of batteries as the D.C motor consumes energy from the batteries. The terminals of the charger are connected to the terminals of the batteries, and with the switch on, the batteries power the DC motor which in turn drives the alternator which then produces electricity having voltage up to 240 V. The output voltage produced is then used to power the loads and as well charge the batteries at the same time with the help of the filter circuit connected to the charger. The electrical components such as diodes and capacitors incorporated in the circuit serve auxiliary functions such as rectification, filtering and smoothing in the system (El-Hassan, 2018). The diodes regulate the direction of current flow and can assist in rectification where required, while the capacitors help stabilize voltage fluctuations and improve the quality of the generated output by smoothing transient variations (Theraja and Theraja, 2005). The entire generator assembly is mounted on a rigid frame to ensure mechanical stability, alignment, and vibration reduction during operation.

Thus, the overall operation of the generator involves a two-stage energy conversion process: electrical energy from the battery drives the DC motor to produce mechanical rotation, and the alternator converts this mechanical energy into usable electrical power through electromagnetic induction. The system is referred to as a "battery-assisted" generator because it does not rely on conventional fuels

such as petrol or diesel, but depends on an external electrical energy source, typically a rechargeable battery as the source for its operations.

Figure 3: Circuit diagram of the battery-assisted generator

Mathematical Model

The modelling of the battery-assisted generator involves the derivation of the system dynamic equation which comprise of the state and output equations which can be used to study the system stability under loaded conditions (Teasdale et al., 2024). To describe the dynamic behaviour of the generator system, the mathematical model is expressed using the transfer function form which is commonly used in control and system analysis of electromechanical systems. The system consists of the DC motor mechanically coupled to an alternator through the fabricated crankshaft. The DC motor converts the electrical energy from the battery to the mechanical energy which is then used to drive the alternator.

The input electrical equation of the DC motor is given from Equation 1:

$$V_m = R_a i_a + L_a \frac{di_a}{dt} + E_b \quad (1)$$

Where R_a is the armature resistance, i_a is the armature current, L_a is the armature inductance of the coil and E_b is the back emf which is given as $K_b \omega_m$ where K_b is the back emf constant and ω_m is the angular speed

Substituting the value of E_b into Equation 1 and taking the Laplace transform gives

$$V(s) = R_a I(s) + LS I(s) + K_b \theta(s) \quad (2)$$

Factorizing Equation 2 gives

$$V(s) = (R_a + LS) I(s) + K_b \theta(s) \quad (3)$$

The mechanical equation of the coupled rotor system is given from Equation 4 as

$$J \frac{d\omega}{dt} + B\omega = T_m - T_L \quad (4)$$

Where J is the combined inertia of motor and alternator, B is the friction coefficient, T_L is the alternator load torque and T_m is the motor torque which is given as $K_t i_a$ where K_t is the motor torque constant. If the load torque is neglected in Equation 4, T_m substituted and taking the Laplace transform gives

$$JS \theta(s) + B \theta(s) = K_T I(s) \quad (5)$$

Factorizing and making $I(s)$ the subject of formula gives

$$I(s) = \left(\frac{JS+B}{K_T} \right) \theta(s) \quad (6)$$

Substituting Equation 6 into Equation 3 gives

$$V(s) = (R_a + LS) \left(\frac{JS+B}{K_T} \right) \theta(s) + K_b \theta(s) \quad (7)$$

Making $\theta(s)$ the subject of formula gives

$$\theta(s) = \left(\frac{K_T}{(R_a+LS)(JS+B)+K_T K_b} \right) V(s) \quad (8)$$

Solving the algebraic equation of Equation 7, the transfer function of the mechanically coupled rotor system is given as

$$\frac{\theta(s)}{V(s)} = \frac{K_T}{(R_a+LS)(JS+B)+K_T K_b} \quad (9)$$

Since the overall output voltage is obtained from the alternator side, the alternator induced voltage will be a function of the alternator constant and the output of the mechanically coupled rotor side and it can be expressed as

$$E_g = K_g \omega \quad (10)$$

Where K_g is the alternator constant

Taking the Laplace transform of Equation 10 and substituting Equation 8 into Equation 10 gives

$$E_g = \left(\frac{K_g K_T}{(R_a+LS)(JS+B)+K_T K_b} \right) V(s) \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the overall transfer function of the fuel-less generator is obtained as

$$\frac{E_g}{V(s)} = \left(\frac{K_g K_T}{(R_a+LS)(JS+B)+K_T K_b} \right) \quad (12)$$

This model shows that (Adewumi and Adelekan, 2020):

- (i) The generator output voltage depends directly on the rotor speed.
- (ii) The rotor speed depends on the motor electrical parameters and mechanical inertia.
- (iii) The system performance is affected by the armature resistance, inductance, friction losses and load torque.

This makes the generator to behave as a coupled electromechanical system whose dynamics are governed by both electrical circuit equations and mechanical rotational dynamics (Omo-Oghogho and Ofomaja, 2025).

Generating System Testing

In order to ascertain the workability, reliability and operating characteristics of the battery-assisted generator, tests were carried out severally on both unloaded and loaded conditions using 12 V, 65 Ah battery with resistive loads, DC motor speed of 1500 rpm and a generator with a capacity of 1 kW and an overall system efficiency of 65 %. The test was carried out for a 30-minutes period and its various readings and measurements of the generator output voltage was measured with a multimeter on AC voltage and the readings were recorded every 5 minutes interval which was to evaluate the output of the generator. This evaluation is intended to establish the conversion efficiency between the DC Source (Battery) input and the AC output. These evaluations include response to variations in input power, input and output voltage, efficiency, voltage and speed regulations.

Evaluation Indices of the Battery-Assisted Generator

1 Efficiency

Efficiency, which is the ratio of AC output power to the DC input power, shows how effectively the DC input power from the battery source converts to the AC output power of the generator system. The higher the efficiency of the system, the lower the energy losses, heat generation, battery discharge rate and operational cost of the system (Ahmed, et al. 2018).

$$P_{eff} = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \times 100 \% \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Where } P_{out} = V_{AC} \times I_{AC} \times pf$$
$$P_{in} = V_{DC} \times I_{DC}$$

Where P_{out} is the power output and P_{in} is the power input, V_{DC} and I_{DC} are input voltage and current, V_{AC} and I_{AC} are output voltage and current, and pf is the power factor equal to 0.85.

2 Voltage Regulation

Voltage regulation is the change in the terminal voltage when the load is reduced from rated full-load to zero, with speed and field current remaining constant (Singh and Verma 2020). It is expressed in percentage and can be expressed mathematically as seen in Equation 14

$$V_{reg} = \frac{V_{NL} - V_{FL}}{V_{FL}} \times 100 \% \quad (14)$$

Where V_{NL} is the voltage value at no-load and V_{FL} is the voltage value at full-load.

This index measures the ability of the inverter to maintain a stable output voltage despite variation in load or input DC voltage. Good voltage regulation ensures that sensitive appliances receive the correct operating voltage and prevents damage or malfunction (Mekhilef, and Kadir, 2010).

3 Speed Regulation

Speed regulation is defined as the percentage change in speed from no-load to full-load. It is a measure of a motor's ability to maintain a nearly constant speed despite changes in the load. It is expressed mathematically in Equation 15

$$N_{\text{reg}} = \frac{N_{\text{No-Load}} - N_{\text{Full-Load}}}{N_{\text{Full-Load}}} \times 100 \% \quad (15)$$

Where $N_{\text{No-Load}}$ is the speed value at no-load and $N_{\text{Full-Load}}$ is the speed value at full-load.

It acts as an indicator of performance stability where a lower regulation percentage represents better and more consistent speed control (Zolfaghari, et al., 2021).

Test for Evaluation Indices

The test carried out on the inverter were as follows:

1 No-load Test

Under No-load test, the output of the alternator was not connected so it supplies no external current. This made the speed to be highest and its current minimal.

2 Loaded Test

After carrying out the no-load test, resistive loads were gradually applied in steps of 10 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 %, and 100 % of rated power and was operated for 1 hour for every load level. At each load level, the following parameters were measured with a multimeter and recorded:

- Output voltage (RMS)
- DC input voltage and current
- Load current

These measured values were used to compute the following performance characteristics

- generator efficiency at every varying load using Equation 13
- voltage regulation using Equation 14
- speed regulation using Equation 15

Result Analysis and Discussions

The readings and measurement taken during the no-load test condition is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Test result on no-load

Time (min)	Battery voltage (V)	Motor current (A)	Speed (rpm)	Output voltage (V)	Output current (I)	Output power (W)
0	12.0	0.00	1500	239.89	0.00	0.00
5	11.88	2.00	1480	238.21	0.00	0.00
10	11.80	2.38	1460	237.92	0.00	0.00
15	11.70	2.63	1450	236.85	0.00	0.00
20	11.63	2.75	1430	236.05	0.00	0.00
25	11.46	2.88	1420	235.78	0.00	0.00
30	11.31	2.96	1400	235.19	0.00	0.00

Under the no-load test, experimental results show that the generator attained a maximum speed of approximately 1500 rpm with an open-circuit voltage of 239.89. It was also observed that as the voltage reduces, the speed of the generator also reduces. Also, the battery current is minimal and no output current flows since it was not connected to any load and the only losses observed were frictional loss due to the coils of the motor and the alternator and core loss due to their laminations.

The readings and measurement taken during the load test conditions is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Test results on load conditions

Loads (%)	Battery voltage (V)	Motor current (A)	Speed (rpm)	Output voltage (V)	Output current (I)	Output power (W)
0	11.83	11.75	1500	239.87	0.00	0.00
10	11.50	17.43	1480	234.20	0.52	100
25	11.40	42.63	1400	230.89	1.31	255
50	11.34	79.53	1300	225.83	2.74	520
75	11.20	109.45	1220	221.15	3.99	750
100	11.00	139.24	1150	217.87	5.43	1002

Under loaded conditions, it was observed that the input voltage, whose source was from the battery terminals ranges from 11.83 V at 0 % load to 11.00 at 100 % load. Also, there was a reduction in the output voltage of the generator as the load increased from 239.87 at 0 % to 217.87 at 100 %. This is due the losses encountered as a result of the loads it was subjected to during the period under experiments. The results also show that the generator was able to deliver at a maximum capacity of 1 kW at full load with an efficiency of approximately 65 %. Voltage and speed regulations of approximately 10 % and 30 % were observed at full load capacity as seen in Figure 2 and found to be consistent with electromechanical energy conversion characteristics.

Figure 4: Chart of performance evaluation indices

Conclusion

This study presented the design, construction and experimental evaluation of a battery-powered electromechanical generator system. The system was analytically modelled using electrical and mechanical dynamic equations and its performance was evaluated through a laboratory-based no-load and load tests under varying operating conditions. The experimental results demonstrate that the generator is capable of delivering stable output voltage within acceptable limits achieving a maximum output of approximately 1 kW at full load. The system exhibited a peak efficiency of about 65 % with efficiency increasing progressively with load due to improved energy utilization. Voltage regulation was observed to be within 2 – 10 % while speed variation, under load condition, reflected expected electromechanical behaviour. These results confirm that the system performs reliably as a coupled energy conversion unit, with output characteristics strongly dependent on input supply, mechanical coupling and load demand. The battery-assisted generator is economical, affordable, easily to construct and has low maintenance cost making it suitable for powering of homes, offices, farms and organization according to its designed power rating. The system demonstrates stable operation, although continuous operation requires external battery charging due to inherent losses.

References

- Adeyemi, A. and Adelekan, O., (2020), Performance Analysis of Motor – Alternator Generator Systems under Varying Load Conditions, *Journal of Electrical Systems*, 16(3), pp. 455 – 463.
- Ahmed, M., Khan, S., and Ali, Z., (2018), Performance Analysis of Single-phase PWM Inverter, *International Journal of Power Electronics*, 10 (2), pp. 145 – 156.

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- Ajav, E. A., and Adewumi, I. O., (2014), Fuel-less Generating Set: Design, Construction and Performance Evaluation, In Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Engineering and Technology Research, August 5 – 7, 3, pp. 258 – 269.
- Ayinla, L., and Yusuf, A. (2018), Design and implementation of an AC power generator using DC motor, In Proceedings of Engineering Conference on Sustainable Development, 1014 – 1022.
- Benhammou, A., Tedjini, H., Hartani, M. A., Ghoniem, R. M., and Alahmer, A., (2023), Accurate and efficient energy management system of fuel cell/battery/supercapacitor/AC and DC generators hybrid electric vehicles. MDPI Journals on Sustainability, 15(13), 10102.
- Chapman, S. J. (2012). Electric Machinery Fundamentals (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Chalal, L., and Rachid, A., (2025), Development of a Digital Twin for Electric Vehicle Emulator: Modeling and Validation, IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics.
- El-Hasan, T. S. (2018), Development of automotive permanent magnet alternator with fully controlled AC/DC converter, MDPI Journal on Energies, 11(2), 274.
- Fitzgerald, A. E., Kingsley, C., and Umans, S. D. (2003). Electric Machinery (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Gamazo-Real, J. C., Vazquez-Sanchez, E., and Gomez-Gil, J. (2024), Position and Speed Control of Brushless DC Motors Using Sensor-less Techniques, IEEE Access, 12, pp. 1 – 15.
- Hanafi, H., Rahim, Z., Hamizan, H., and Fadzulli, A. F., (2024), Analysis of battery-based and direct current generator drone power system. International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology, 72(5), pp. 216 – 226.
- Mekhilef, S., and Kadir, M. N., (2010), Voltage control of three stage hybrid multilevel inverter using vector transformation, IEEE Transaction on Power Electronics, 25 (10), pp. 2599 – 2606.
- Muktar, S, Bonde, D. S., and Bonde, A. B., (2025), Design, Construction and Performance Evaluation of a Fuel-less Generator, International Journal of Innovative Scientific and Engineering Technologies Research, 13(4), pp. 180 – 189.
- Omo-Oghogho, I., and Ofomaja, M. (2025), Design and performance analysis of a flywheel-assisted motor-generator system, Energy Engineering Journal, 12(1), pp. 55 – 67.

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Roberts, C., Lara, J. D., Henriquez-Auba, R., Poolla, B. K., and Callaway, D. S., (2020), Grid-Coupled Dynamic Response of Battery-Driven Voltage Source Converters, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, 35(6), pp. 456 – 468.

Singh, R., and Verma, P., (2020), Voltage Regulation Analysis of Low-power Inverter System, Journal of Electrical Engineering, 71 (4), pp. 289 – 297

Supriyatna, D., (2023), Analysis of power efficiency produced by AC and DC generators: A literature review, Motivection Journal of Mechanical, Electrical and Industrial Engineering, 5(2), pp. 261 – 268.

Teasdale, A., Ishaku, L., Amaechi, C. V., Adelusi, I., and Abdelazim, A. (2024), A Study on an Energy-Regenerative Braking Model Using Supercapacitors and DC Motors, MDPI World Electric Vehicle Journal, 15(7), 326.

Theraja, B. L., and Theraja, A. K. (2005). A Textbook of Electrical Technology, Vol. II: AC and DC Machines. S. Chand Publishing.

Zolfaghari, H., Karimi, H., and Momeni, H. (2021), Voltage Stabilization of DC Microgrid Using ANFIS Controller, Electric Power Systems Research, 196, pp. 107 – 118.

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